

RUTTER

Kick-off meeting

17 January 2020

Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade de Lisboa
Building C8, room 8.2.13

Proceedings

Edited by Silvana Munzi

Program

17 January 2020

Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade de Lisboa, Building C8, room 8.2.13

- 10:00-10:45 *Why Rutters? Goals and methods of the RUTTER Project*
Henrique Leitão
- 10:45-11:15 *What are we working with?*
Joana Lima and José Maria Moreno Madrid
- 11:15-11:45 *Arab Navigation until the XVI century: A State of the Art*
Inês Bénard da Costa and Carlos Paiva Neves
- 11.45-12:00 Break
- 12:00-13:00 **Rutter Seminar**
Formal and informal patterns of globalisation. Early Modern empire building
Amélia Polónia
- 13:00-15:00 Lunch
- 15:00-15:30 *From Atlantic history to Early Modern education: the historiographical importance of integrating local and global dimensions*
David Salomoni
- 15:30-16:00 *From alphanumeric cosmology to the (Arab...ish) dominion of the seas*
Juan Acevedo
- 16:00-16:30 *Coming to the Surface: The Ecclesiastical Libraries in Portugal until 1834*
Luana Giurgevich
- 16:30-17:00 *Jan Huygen van Linschoten (1562-1611), the Portuguese Empire and the Netherlands: transmission of knowledge in the second half of the XVI century*
Nuno Vila-Santa
- 17:00-17:30 Final discussion

Abstracts

RUTTER seminar

Formal and informal patterns of globalization in the Early Modern period

Amélia Polónia, Universidade de Porto

asilva@letras.up.pt

The talk aims at offering an overview of some recent individual and team research' results, focused on the analysis of European, mostly Portuguese Overseas Expansion. It presents cooperation and self-organisation as global patterns taken as essential to the building, sustainability and collapse of European colonial empires in the Early Modern Period. Finally, it aims at giving a glimpse on the role of individuals and informal networks in the building of a global world in the Early Modern Period, according to a bottom-up approach.

Oral presentations

Why Rutters? Goals and methods of the RUTTER Project

Henrique Leitão

hjleitao@fc.ul.pt

Why are rutters important? (What are rutters anyway?) And what are the objectives of our Project? that is, what are our goals (the explicit and the not-so explicit) and how can we check if we are meeting them?

RUTTER is an ambitious and complex Project; but where exactly is the ambition and the complexity? So, what lies ahead? How should we move on? What will happen if we succeed? -- and if we fail?

This presentation will attempt to clarify these questions and many others. It is, in a sense, a rutter for the RUTTER Project.

What are we working with?

Joana Lima and José Maria Moreno Madrid
joanalimadeoliveira@gmail.com; jmoren04@ucm.es

Rocking the historiographical boat is not easy. One could not do it without a solid documental basis, so that is what we have been compiling for the last months and will be now presenting. Having in mind that this is not a final version of the Portuguese and Spanish rutter corpus from the 16th, 17th and 18th centuries, and that we still did not get our hands dirty in the archives, since this has been an online search, the 2500 documents we collected are not something to undervalue. One could not also do it without defining what does rutter literature consist of – nautical rutters, nautical guides, seamen handbooks – and what other textual typologies are crucial to our project – travel reports, ship logbooks, documentation about laws, royal decrees and letters. Despite these types of documents being common to both Portuguese and Spanish Crowns, we must analyse the corpora separately regarding the differences in documental and archive history in both countries, which may provoke two diverse mindsets in our research activity. Thus, the Portuguese corpus will be presented, highlighting the most significant works we will be working with, and explaining how this documentation is comprised in archives all over the world. Being the Spanish case quite different, since most of the documentation is collected in Spanish archives, the corpus will be presented, focusing on the documentation of the main archives. Hold on to this boat, these are exciting waters we are entering.

Arab Navigation until the XVI century: A State of the Art

Inês Bénard da Costa and Carlos Paiva Neves
inesbenardc@gmail.com; carlsete@hotmail.com

The historiography of Arabic navigation in the Indian ocean, the Red sea and the Persian Gulf is relatively recent. The opportunity to explore questions regarding the navigators, the paths they followed, or the techniques and instruments they used, came only after the end of the 19th century – when Arabic texts on navigation were first encountered. Much has been developed since then. Transcriptions, translations, glossaries and topographical studies of Ibn Majid's and Sulaymān al-Mahrī's texts gave historians a better understanding, not only of specific sea rutters, but also about Arabic nautical science. New questions naturally followed, concerning – for instance – the two known authors' navigation schools or traditions. Yet, when looking into the most recent historical studies, it seems that modern historiography has come to a stagnation point: It remains centred in the same authors for the last century.

This presentation proposes a brief state of the art of Arabic navigation in the Indian Ocean until the sixteenth century. It summarizes both the primary sources that have been known so far, and the main studies that have been published – regarding not only rutters specifically, but Arabic

navigation in general. Although it will not thoroughly discuss nautical techniques and instruments, this presentation will regard them briefly so that – at the end – the audience can have an idea of how Arabic navigation is seen by modern historians.

From Atlantic history to Early Modern education: the historiographical importance of integrating local and global dimensions

David Salomoni

david.salomoni@uniroma3.it

In the course of this presentation I will outline the research topics that I have dealt with over the years. The talk, however, will not be a simple linear narration of my objects of study. It will be an attempt to highlight what has been the methodological continuity that I have tried to impress in each research. For each object of study, it was a matter of finding the links between the local and global dimensions of historical phenomena. No scholar, in fact, would deny a connection between these two dimensions, but trying to make an investigation on a documentary basis is not always evident. Finding these links has been at the core of my work as a historian. These examples will cover two main topics. The first is the circulation of ideas in the Atlantic area during the American Revolution, between two “peripheries” of the 18th century western world such as the British colonies of North America and the small pre-unitary Italian states. The second theme concerns the importance of the small centres of education and rural evangelization belonging to the Jesuits and to other religious orders in Early modern Italy. In this way, therefore, I want to offer some examples of what will be the methodological approach that I will bring and integrate with the RUTTER project.

From alphanumeric cosmology to the (Arab...ish) dominion of the seas

Juan Acevedo

juan.acevedo.juan@gmail.com

I will explain how I ended up studying what is essentially physics from a typographical angle – starting from Classics and Hebrew, through Arabic and Islamic Studies, to talismans and magic spells. All this is centered on a little Greek word: *stoicheion*, at once a letter, a number and an element, and therefore on the idea that you can spell, count and recount reality and so control it, because alphabets and periodic tables are essentially alike. How much of this applies to the ocean? What was the ‘alphabet’ of blue water navigation? The 32 points of the compass like the 32 ‘ways’ used by God to create the world in the *Sefer Yetsirah*?

Coming to the surface: The Ecclesiastical libraries in Portugal until 1834

Luana Giurgevich

luana.giurgevich@gmail.com

In Modern Portugal religious institutions organised impressive collections of books, by far the largest in the country. These libraries not only served the religious institutions themselves, but also supplied books to lesser libraries, such as the University Library of Coimbra and the Royal Library. The Portuguese book market depended above all on the interests, choices and cultural relations of these peculiar book collectors. Documentary evidence has proved the existence of approximately 400 institutional libraries in Portugal until 1834. After the dissolution of religious orders in Portugal in the 1830's, the book collections were widely dispersed within the National Library and among a myriad of institutions, each with its own curatorial traditions and practices. Mapping all extant library inventories and catalogues become a crucial task in the reconstruction of the whole universe of Portuguese ecclesiastical libraries and make possible to analyze the composition of these libraries.

Jan Huygen van Linschoten (1562-1611), the Portuguese Empire and the Netherlands: transmission of knowledge in the second half of the XVI century

Nuno Vila-Santa

gemeo1984@hotmail.com

Author of the famous *Itinerario*, Jan Huygen van Linschoten (1562-1611) was a Dutch sailor, cartographer, merchant and “politician”, who played a crucial role in the transmission of knowledge between the Portuguese Empire and the Netherlands.

In his book, first published in 1596, supported by the highest Dutch authorities of his time, Linschoten provided wide and systematized information on Portuguese Asia: politics, economy, society, science, navigation, etc. The *Itinerario* was rapidly translated into English, German and French. Thus, Linschoten's work is generally associated with the beginning of the Dutch Expansion, especially due to his publication, the *Reys-gheschrift*, of the main Portuguese rutters, which were of crucial importance for the first Dutch expedition to Asia in 1595-97.

This communication will attempt to explain the importance of studying Linschoten's work for the Rutter project. In order to achieve this goal, I will also speak briefly how I come to choose this topic, within the project aims, and also how this is related to all my previous research on the broader field of the Portuguese-Asian relations in the second half of the XVI century. Having studied the Portuguese “Estado da Índia”, especially in the period 1548-1580, on the political, military, religious, economic, social and cultural grounds, I will attempt to show how my previous research is related to the main topic I will address: the transmission of knowledge between the Portuguese and Dutch empires and, afterwards, its truly “globalisation”.

Acknowledgements

European Research Council

Established by the European Commission

CIUHCT

Centro Interuniversitário de História
das Ciências e da Tecnologia
FCUL | FCT - UNL

**Ciências
ULisboa**